

Bimetallic Complexes involving Schiff Base

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Manuscript received 6 May 1985, revised 19 May 1986, accepted 18 June 1986

Phenylmercury derivative (phHgSA) of Schiff base SAH derived from salicylaldehyde and aniline have been prepared. Reaction of this derivative with $M(NCS)_2$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II} , gave complexes of general formulae $(phHgSA)_2M(NCS)_2$. These complexes on further reaction with pyridine or bipyridine (L) furnished adducts of general formula $(phHgSA)_2M(NCS)_2L_x$, where $x = 1$ or 2. All the complexes have been characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight, molar conductance, infrared and electronic spectral data. On the basis of these studies, probable structure of the complexes and quantitative softness parameters have been evaluated.

STUDIES on bimetallic complexes have been the subject-matter of interest in the recent years^{1,2}. Bimetallic compounds with and without thiocyanate bridge are known³⁻⁶. A new type of bimetallic compounds involving phenylmercury derivative of Schiff base have been reported in the present paper.

Experimental

$M(NCS)_2$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II} , were prepared by reacting the respective metal nitrates with potassium thiocyanate in ethanol medium. The Schiff base salicylidine-aniline (SAH) was prepared by the reported procedure⁹. Phenylmercury chloride was prepared from the acetate by reaction with potassium chloride in ethanol. All the other chemicals were AnalaR grade.

Phenylmercury derivative (phHgSA) of salicylidine-aniline: Sodium metal (1 g) was dissolved in isopropyl alcohol (25 ml). The Schiff base (SAH) (1.92 g) was separately dissolved in benzene. The two solutions were mixed and refluxed for 1 h. The excess solvent was distilled off and the solution cooled, when light yellow crystals of the sodium derivative (NaSA) separated, which was filtered, washed with benzene and stored in vacuum desiccator as it was air-sensitive. The compound was dissolved in dry acetone and mixed with an acetone solution of phenylmercury chloride in 1:1 molar ratio and stirred for 2 h. Sodium chloride separated, was filtered. On addition of water to the clear filtrate, phenylmercury derivatives (phHgSA) of the Schiff base (SAH) precipitated, and it was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum. The compound was subjected to elemental analysis.

Complexes $(phHgSA)_2M(NCS)_2$, ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II}): phHgSA (9.4 g, 2 mmol) was dissolved in solvent (25 ml) consisting of 50% ethyl acetate and acetone (solution 'A'). $Co(NCS)_2$ (1.75 g, 1 mmol) was separately dissolved in 25 ml of the same solvent (25 ml) (solution 'B'). Solution 'A'

and 'B' were mixed and refluxed for 10 h, when $(phHgSA)_2Co(NCS)_2$ separated out as a blue solid. It was filtered, washed with the same solvent and dried in vacuum. The other complexes, where $M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II} were prepared similarly.

Adducts $[(phHgSA)_2M(NCS)_2L_x]$ ($L = py, bipy$; $x = 1$ or 2): To a suspension of $(phHgSA)_2Co(NCS)_2$ (2.8 g, 1 mmol) in ethyl acetate (25 ml) was added pyridine (2 ml, 2 mmol) dissolved in acetone (25 ml), and stirred for 12 h when the adducts $(phHgSA)_2Co(NCS)_2L_2$ separated out as a pink solid. It was filtered, washed with acetone and recrystallised from dimethyl sulphoxide. The adducts of bipyridine was prepared by similar procedure. The adducts for the other complexes, where $M = Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II} were similarly prepared.

Analytical results of the complexes are stated in Table 1.

The molar conductance values of the complexes were measured in dimethyl sulphoxide using a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. The molecular weights were determined cryoscopically using dmso as the solvent. The infrared spectra (4 000 - 200 cm^{-1}) were recorded in nujol by a Pye Unicam sp 3-300 spectrophotometer, and the electronic spectra by a Pye Unicam sp 5-500 UV visible spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature by Gouy's method using $CoHg(SCN)_4$ as the standard. The diamagnetic correction was made using Pascal's constant¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Lewis acids: The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes of the type $(phHgSA)_2M(NCS)_2$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and Zn^{II} showed two bands at 18 450 and 10 000 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^4T_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ (ν_3) and ${}^4T_1 \rightarrow {}^4A_2$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively. Various spectral parameters Dq , B' and β (Table 2) have been calculated¹¹ from

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Molecular weight Found/ (Calcd.)	M. p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B. M.
				Hg	S	M	N		
phHgSA	Light yellow	320 (474)	115	40.6 (42.1)	—	—	2.3 (2.1)	38.5	—
(phHgSA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ 2py	Blue	936 (1 123)	175	32.5 (35.6)	5.0 (5.6)	5.0 (5.2)	4.8 (4.9)	40.0	4.3
(phHgSA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ bipy	Pink	1 100 (1 281)	180d	32.0 (31.2)	4.4 (4.9)	4.26 (4.6)	4.0 (4.3)	45.6	5.2
(phHgSA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ bipy	Orange	1 040 (1 277)	200	28.0 (31.3)	4.5 (5.5)	4.5 (4.6)	4.6 (4.3)	42.0	5.01
(phHgSA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂	Green	1 120 (1 122.9)	185d	32.5 (35.6)	4.7 (5.0)	5.02 (5.2)	4.7 (4.9)	45.3	3.14
(phHgSA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ 2py	Yellow	1 110 (1 280.9)	210d	31.1 (31.2)	4.2 (5.0)	4.4 (4.6)	4.2 (4.3)	48.9	3.18
(phHgSA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ bipy	Yellow	1 005 (1 276.9)	195d	29.2 (31.3)	4.5 (5.0)	4.45 (4.6)	4.02 (4.3)	45.6	3.0
(phHgSA) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂	Yellow	910 (1 127)	240d	32.5 (35.9)	4.8 (5.6)	5.45 (5.5)	4.8 (4.9)	54.3	2.02
(phHgSA) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ 2py	Yellow	980 (1 285)	230d	30.8 (31.1)	4.9 (4.9)	4.85 (4.9)	4.25 (4.3)	36.3	2.09
(phHgSA) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ bipy	Yellow	1 020 (1 281)	180d	28.9 (31.2)	4.5 (4.9)	4.6 (4.9)	4.0 (4.3)	57.5	2.17
(phHgSA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂	White	890 (1 129)	270d	32.8 (35.4)	5.2 (5.6)	4.7 (5.7)	3.99 (4.9)	57.3	—
(phHgSA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂ 2py	White	1 115 (1 287)	240d	31.4 (31.0)	5.0 (4.9)	5.0 (5.0)	4.05 (4.3)	60.6	—
(phHgSA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂ bipy	White	945 (1 283)	245d	31.25 (31.1)	4.5 (4.9)	4.2 (5.0)	3.98 (4.3)	61.5	—

d = Decomposition temp.

TABLE 2—QUANTITATIVE SOFTNESS PARAMETERS IN THE FORMATION OF ADDUCTS [REACTION BETWEEN phHgSAM(NCS)₂+ Py or bipy, (SA)₂M(NCS)₂+ Py or bipy]

Compd.	$E_{n(sff)}^+$ of M in Lewis acids	$E_{n(sff)}^+$ N-end in py or bipy	$E_{n,m}^+$	CFSE	Matching constant	Stability constant
(phHgSA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ 2py	-1.84	-11.11	9.27	6.39	15.66	5.28
(phHgSA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ 2py	-2.34	-11.11	8.78	4.19	12.98	4.35
(phHgSA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂ 2py	-3.99	-11.11	7.12	—	7.62	3.22
(SA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ 2py	-1.75	-11.11	9.36	6.40	16.76	5.29
(SA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ 2py	-2.32	-11.11	8.79	4.27	13.66	4.60
(SA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂ 2py	-3.96	11.11	7.15	—	7.15	3.27
(phHgSA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ bipy	-1.86	-11.06	9.22	6.40	15.62	5.38
(phHgSA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ bipy	-2.34	-11.06	7.82	4.21	11.83	4.02
(phHgSA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂ bipy	-3.99	-11.06	7.07	—	7.07	3.50
(SA) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ bipy	-1.75	-11.06	8.36	6.41	15.78	5.40
(SA) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ bipy	-2.32	-11.06	8.76	4.22	12.97	4.30
(SA) ₂ Zn(NCS) ₂ bipy	-3.96	-11.06	7.10	—	7.10	3.50

ν_3 and ν_2 bands positions. The position of the bands, spectral parameters and magnetic moment values indicate tetrahedral geometry around Co^{II} in the complexes.

Ni^{II} complexes of this series gave three bands at 27 000, 17 600 and 10 020 cm⁻¹ to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (ν_3), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (F) (ν_2) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} (F) (ν_1) transitions, respectively. The magnetic moment value is 3.14 B.M. The positions of these bands, spectral parameters and magnetic moment values indicate an octahedral geometry for Ni^{II} in these complexes where thiocyanate group of the adjacent layer¹³ provided axial coordination. Spectral data at 15 300 cm⁻¹ and magnetic moment value of 2.02 B.M. of Cu^{II} complexes are in agreement with octahedral geometry around Cu^{II}.

phHgSA has only one site for bonding, viz. the nitrogen of CH=N moiety. The ν_{CH-N} band¹³ shifted from 1 610 to 1 635 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination of CH=N moiety to metal ion. The bands diagnostic of ν_{C-N} , ν_{C-S} , δ_{NOS} of the thiocyanate group appeared at 2 110–2 090, 780–700 cm⁻¹ and 470–430 cm⁻¹, respectively. The positions of these bands were indicative of N-bonded thiocyanate¹⁴.

Additional band appearing in the region 400–300 cm⁻¹ in the metal complex as compared to the derivative of Schiff base can be assigned to M–N frequencies¹⁵. All the complexes were non-conducting in nature and were monomeric. On the basis of these results the structures (b) and (c) (Fig. 1) could be proposed.

Fig. 1

Adduct $(\text{phHgSA})_2\text{M}(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}_x$, where $\text{L} = \text{py}$, bipy ; $x = 1$ or 2 : The electronic spectra of the Co^{2+} complexes of this series gave three bands at 21 370–21 580, 17 000–17 700 and 10 000–10 010 cm^{-1} , which correspond to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3), ${}^4\text{T}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ (ν_1) transitions, respectively. The Ni^{2+} complexes showed three bands at 26 690–26 400, 16 690–16 600 and 10 020–10 010 cm^{-1} , which were assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3), ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_1) transitions, respectively. The position of the bands the Dq , B' and β values and the magnetic moment data (Table 2) indicate octahedral geometry around Co^{2+} and in Ni^{2+} in these complexes. The Dq values^{16,17} of the complexes formed by SAH with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} are higher than that of the corresponding complexes of phHgSA . Thus phHgSA is a weaker donor than SAH.

The infrared spectra of the adducts showed no significant change in the position of ν_{ON} , ν_{OS} and δ_{NOS} and $\nu_{\text{O-N}}$ bands. A negative shift was observed for the $\nu_{\text{M-NOS}}$ bands in case of cobalt and zinc complexes due to the change in coordination geometry from tetrahedral to octahedral^{18,19}. Such a change was not observed for Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complexes as the geometry around these metal ions was already octahedral in the $(\text{phHgSA})_2\text{M}(\text{NCS})_2$ complexes. Ring vibrations of pyridine and bipyridyl at 405 and 604 cm^{-1} shifted to higher frequency by about 25 cm^{-1} in the adducts indicating their coordination^{20,21} to the metal ions. The positive shift in ring vibration at 900 and 1 500 cm^{-1} also showed feature of coordination through ring nitrogen. All the adducts were non-conducting in dmsO. On the basis of these results, the structures (c) and (d) (Fig. 1) could be proposed for the adducts

Quantitative softness values: The softness of metal ions has been denoted by E_m^+ , of base ions

by E_n^+ and the difference between the two ΔE_{nm}^+ . Softness parameters of various metal ions and bases involved in the present series have been calculated by the method described elsewhere²², and applied to find out the comparative donor strength of SAH and phHgSA towards $\text{M}(\text{NCS})_2$. The matching constant values (Table 2) showed that SAH is a better donor than phHgSA . Phenylmercury substitution on SAH decreased its donor ability.

Complexes of Schiff base and of phenylmercury derivative of Schiff base have been prepared. Both the complexes act as Lewis acid because of unsaturation at $\text{M}(\text{II})$. The comparative acceptor strength of $\text{M}(\text{II})$ in both the complexes have been evaluated with the help of softness parameters. The softness parameters reveal that $\text{M}(\text{II})$ in SAH complex is better acceptor than in phHgSA . This has been established by reacting the two Lewis acids with pyridine. Pyridine forms more stable complexes $(\text{SAH})_2\text{M}(\text{NCS})_2$ than with $(\text{phHgSA})_2\text{M}(\text{NCS})_2$. The order of stability of adducts was formed to be $\text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support from C.S.I.R., New Delhi.

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